

Kinetic of base hydrolysis of some (aminomonocarboxylato)bis(ethylenediamine)/(trimethylenediamine) Co^{III} complexes in aqueous medium

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Abstract : *cis*-[(en)₂Co(O₂CCH₂NH₃)₂]³⁺, *cis*-[(en)₂Co(β-O₂C(CH₂)₂NH₃)₂]³⁺ and *trans*-[(tmd)₂Co(O₂CCH₂NH₃)₂]³⁺ were synthesized. The base hydrolysis of these complexes proceed through a two step mechanism.

A D_{cb} mechanism has been proposed for the reaction.

Keywords : Kinetics, hydrolysis, amino acid complex, cobalt(III).

Introduction

Some fifty years ago the base hydrolysis of a series of complexes of the type *trans*-[(en)₂Co(O₂CC₆H₄X)₂]⁺ (X = *p*-OCH₃, *p*-CH₃, *m*-CH₃, *p*-Cl, *m*-F, *m*-NO₂) and *cis*- and *trans*-[Co(en)₂(O₂CR)₂]⁺ (R = alkyl group) was studied and S_N1 cb mechanism involving Co-O bond fission was proposed¹. In the present work, we have reported the kinetics and mechanism of base hydrolysis of some amino acid complexes of cobalt(III) like bis(aminomonocarboxylato)bis(en/tmd)cobalt(III) complexes.

Results and discussion

The complexes, *cis*-[(en)₂Co(O₂CCH₂NH₃)₂]³⁺ and *cis*-[(en)₂Co(β-O₂C(CH₂)₂NH₃)₂]³⁺, exhibit absorption maxima at 500 and 360 nm with ε (dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) as 93, 150 and 170, 113 respectively which closely agree with the reported values {λ_{max}, nm (ε, dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)} : 500 (94), 360 (154) and 500 (171), 360 (115) for glycinate and β-alaninato complexes respectively². Acidification of the reaction mixture after base hydrolysis leads to the formation of the dihydroxo complexes in each case³. {λ_{max}, nm (ε, dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)} : 500 (84) and 360 (69) which correspond with the reported values of *cis*-[(en)₂Co(OH₂)₂]³⁺; {λ_{max}, nm (ε, dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)} : 495 (81) and 360 (70)³. Similarly acidification of the reaction mixture after base hydrolysis of *trans*-

[(tmd)₂Co(O₂CCH₂NH₃)₂]³⁺ to pH ~ 1 displayed {λ_{max}, nm (ε, dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)} : 510 (50) and 360 (64) respectively⁴ which agreed with that of *cis*-[(tmd)₂Co(OH₂)₂]³⁺; {λ_{max}, nm (ε, dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹)} : 500 (51) and 360 (65) respectively⁴. The absorbance-time data (Fig. 1) for run confirms to a two step process and the data for each step fitted excellently well to a single exponential equation. Thus indicating that the base hydrolysis of these complexes conform to a two step reaction at different time scales of measurement which may be delineated as in Scheme 1.

where AA denotes en and tmd; X denotes glycinate, β-alaninato ligands. Similar observations was reported for the base hydrolysis of *trans*-[(en)₂Co(O₂CC₆H₄X)₂]⁺ (X = *p*-OCH₃, *p*-CH₃, *m*-CH₃, *p*-Cl, *m*-F, *m*-NO₂) and *cis*- and *trans*-[(en)₂Co(O₂CR)₂]⁺ (R = aliphatic carboxylic acid)¹.

Rate data for the fast and slow steps are displayed in Figs. 2 and 3 showing k_{obs}^{fast} vs [OH⁻] and k_{obs}^{slow} vs [OH⁻]

Fig. 1. Plot of absorbance vs time at 25 °C complex, $\text{cis-}[(\text{en})_2\text{Co}(\text{gly})_2]^+$, $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (1) and $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (2), $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4).

respectively for different Co^{III} centres at different temperatures. The pseudo-first-order rate constants for both the steps obeyed the relationship.

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{OH}}^x [\text{OH}^-]$$

where x stands for fast or slow step ($k_{\text{OH}}^{\text{fast}}$ and $k_{\text{OH}}^{\text{slow}}$) value and their activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are collected in Table 1.

The second order base hydrolysis rate constant, $k_{\text{OH}}^{\text{fast}}$, for both (en) analogues are comparable to each other but (tmd)(glycinato)₂ complex reacts ~ 12 and 20 times faster than the (en)₂(glycinato)₂ and (en)₂(β-alaninato)₂ analogues respectively. In the slow step, glycinato complex reacts ~ 2 times faster than the β-alaninato analogue of the (en) complex indicating thereby that the coordinated glycinate presumably enhance the pK_{NH} of the coordinated (en) to a greater extent than the β-alaninate, under identical experimental condition. Similar pK_{NH} perturbation in the base hydrolysis of $\alpha\beta\text{S-}[(\text{tetren})\text{Co}(\beta\text{-alaninato})]^{2+}$ has been observed⁵, the possibility that glycinate is a better leaving group than the β-alaninate, however cannot be overlooked. The reactivity sequence for the slow step, $k_{\text{OH}}^{\text{slow}}$, follows the sequence : (tmd)₂Co(glycinato-O)(OH) > (en)₂Co(glycinato-O)(OH) > (en)₂Co(β-alaninato-O)(OH).

Fig. 2. Plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ for fast step at 25 °C (1), 30 °C (2), 35 °C (3), 40 °C (4) for complex $\text{cis-}[(\text{en})_2\text{Co}(\text{gly})_2]^+$: $[\text{Complex}] = 3.00 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4), $\lambda = 280 \text{ nm}$.

The high positive activation enthalpy (ΔH^\ddagger) for all the complexes in both the steps indicated that $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1$ cb mechanism involving Co-O bond fission is valid for both this steps. However, the low and negative activation entropy (ΔS^\ddagger) point to the greater solvent ordering by their conjugate bases in the transition state.

Table 1. Rate constants for slow and fast steps of hydrolysis
 $10^3 k \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$

Temp. (°C)	<i>cis</i> -[(en) ₂ Co(gly) ₂] ⁺	<i>cis</i> -[(en) ₂ Co(β-alaninato) ₂] ⁺	<i>trans</i> -[tmd) ₂ Co(gly) ₂] ⁺
Slow step :			
10.0	0.94 ± 0.04	0.35 ± 0.02	1.77 ± 0.06
15.0	1.49 ± 0.03	0.71 ± 0.02	3.20 ± 0.02
20.0	2.70 ± 0.12	1.40 ± 0.03	4.99 ± 0.13
25.0	4.41 ± 0.10	1.72 ± 0.18	-
$\Delta H^\ddagger/\text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	75.4 ± 4.1	88.5 ± 9.4	69.2 ± 5.2
$\Delta S^\ddagger/\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	21 ± 13	2 ± 32	5 ± 18
Fast step :			
20.0	1.15 ± 0.05	-	10.6 ± 0.3
25.0	2.00 ± 0.12	1.20 ± 0.04	23.4 ± 0.5
30.0	-	1.80 ± 0.17	40.9 ± 1.0
35.0	5.10 ± 0.24	2.80 ± 0.05	92.0 ± 2.0
40.0	9.20 ± 0.22	5.20 ± 0.22	177 ± 4
$\Delta H^\ddagger/\text{kJ mol}^{-1}$	76.6 ± 2.3	68.3 ± 7.2	104 ± 3
$\Delta S^\ddagger/\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	-21 ± 7	-53 ± 23	92 ± 11

Experimental

cis-[(en)₂(glyH/alaH)₂Co](ClO₄)₃ (glyH = glycine, alaH = alanine) were prepared starting from *cis*-[(en)₂CoCO₃]NO₃. The carbonato complex (0.01 mol) was treated with required amount ~ 4 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄ and warmed to expel dissolve CO₂. 0.03 mol of glycine/alanine was added to this solution and pH of the mixture was adjusted to 4–5 (for glycine) or ~ 3 (for alanine). The solution was evaporated at ~ 50 °C for 5–6 h and then refrigerated overnight when the red colour crystals of desired complex obtained. For recrystallization, the solid was dissolved in HClO₄ (0.1 mol dm⁻³) and the solution was filtered to ice-cold HClO₄. The red crystals were collected, washed successfully with ice-cold ethanol, diethyl ether and stored over fused calcium chloride. *trans*-[Co(tmd)₂(glyH)₂](ClO₄) (tmd = trimethyldiamine) was prepared from the corresponding carbonate complex in a similar manner. Found for [A₂CoX₂](ClO₄)₃; Co, 9.4; C, 15.4; H, 4.9; N, 13.2; (A = en, X = glyH) : Co, 8.97; C, 18.4; H, 4.6; N, 12.8; (A = en, X = alaH) : Co, 8.7; C, 18.0; H, 4.4; N, 12.3; (A = tmd, X = glyH) : calcd. for [A₂CoX₂](ClO₂)₃ : Co 9.39; C, 15.3; H, 4.1; N, 13.4; (A = en, X = gly) : Co, 8.99; C, 18.3; H, 4.6; N, 12.8; (A = en, X = alaH) : Co, 8.79; C, 17.8; H, 4.7; N, 12.5; (A = tmd, X = glyH).

Fig. 3. Plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ for slow step at 10 °C (1), 15 °C (2), 20 °C (3), 25 °C (4) for complex *cis*-[(en)₂Co(gly)₂]⁺ : [Complex] = $3.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO₄), $\lambda = 500 \text{ nm}$.

AnalaR grade chemicals were used. The solutions were prepared in freshly prepared distilled water. The second distillation being made from alkaline KMnO₄ in an all glass distillation apparatus.

A Jasco 7800 UV-Visible spectrophotometer and Hitech (UK) SF51 stopped flow spectrophotometer interfaced with an Apple II GS PC was used for all spectral and kinetics measurements. The C, H, N analysis was made at CDRI, Lucknow, India.

Kinetics :

The fast kinetics of base hydrolysis was studied at 20 < *t*/°C < 40 by stopped flow spectrophotometry under pseudo-first-order conditions with $[\text{OH}^-]_{\text{T}}$ varying from 0.1 to 0.5 mol dm⁻³, $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [complex] = $3.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The decrease of absorbance with time was monitored at 280 nm. The kinetics of slow step was studied by conventional spectrophotometry. Aliquots (5 ml) of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at known time intervals and acidified with HClO₄ to quench the reaction and decrease of absorbance was measured at 500 nm. The rate constants were calculated from the gradients of $\ln (A_t - A_\infty)$ vs *t* (s) plots from the relationship

$$\ln |(A_t - A_\infty)| = \ln |A_0 - A_\infty| - k_{\text{obs}}.t$$

Note

where A_0 , A_t , A_∞ denote optical density of the reaction mixture at zero time, time ' t ' and infinite time (ca. $10 t_{1/2}$) respectively. Runs were made duplicate and average rate constant were recorded accordingly. All calculations were made on IBM 486 PC using least squares program.

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